

ROLE OF NATIONAL GREEN TRIBUNAL (NGT) IN ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE

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Abstract

According to Art. 21 of the Constitution of India it is fundamental right to everyone i.e. Human Being and Life Being to live in natural environment which is free from any pollution. Now a days in this modern world most cities affected with the Air Pollution and Water Pollution. It was recommendation of Supreme Court of India in many cases there should be a separate authority to deal with the matters relating to environmental issues. And finally, the National Green Tribunal has been established on 18th October, 2010 under the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010. The National Green Tribunal (NGT) is a statutory body that plays a crucial role in environmental governance by providing a specialized, expeditious, and quasi-judicial forum for environmental dispute resolution. Established under the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010, its mandate includes the effective and prompt disposal of cases related to environmental protection, conservation of forests and natural resources, and the enforcement of legal rights concerning the environment. The NGT ensures environmental justice by providing timely remedies and compensation for damages, reducing the burden on higher courts, and promoting adherence to environmental laws. This research paper provide the details of different roles of NGT in Dispute Resolution, Environmental Law Enforcement, Compensation and Relief, Expeditious Disposal, Specialized Expertise, Promoting Environmental Jurisprudence, Broad Jurisdiction of the National Green Tribunal. The National Green Tribunal is successful in speedy disposal of cases relating to environmental laws. And National Green Tribunal is a strong pillar in environmental justice system in India.

Keywords: -Right to life, Environmental Pollution, Role of NGT

1) INTRODUCTION: -

The National Green Tribunal is Established by the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010, therefore National Green Tribunal (NGT) is one of the Statutory body. The primary aim of the national Green Tribunal is to dispose environmental cases in speedily particularly

protection of environment and pollution cases. Likewise other countries in the world India is third on number which is establish the National Green Tribunal by way of Statute.in the New Zealand and Australia this type of Tribunal Already existed.in India the Head office of the National Green Tribunal is at New Delhi and the regional Head offices is located at metro cities like Bhopal, Pune, Kolkata, and Chennai.¹

Till now The National Green Tribunal disposed many important decisions like declared using diesel vehicles more than fifteen years old running on road in New Delhi is unlawful in protection of the air and prevent the air pollution. The National Green Tribunal Also Given one of the landmark judgments relating to Sunerban in Kolkata for prevention of noise pollution by way of banning construction Activities and solid wastes. The National Green Tribunal utmost take care of Sunderban as an eco-sensitive region to protect the wildlife. Green Tribunal is a quasi- Judicial Authority which have multiple powers to issue orders to the government and public bodies. Suo moto cation can be taken on the issues of environment. This National Green Tribunal also have a wide power to impose penalties on wrong doers.²

2) RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: -

In the Present Paper the Researcher adopted the doctrinal method which is based upon the laws relating to National Green Tribunal and its composition, its effectiveness and judicial activism. In the past years the National Green Tribunal delivered many judgments in protection of the Environment. decisions given by the Tribunal is data for analysis in the research to prove the role of National Green Tribunal in Environment Governance.

3) REVIEW OF LITERATURE: -

The Researcher carefully observe the Provisions of The Green Tribunal Act,2010 and its commentary in the textbooks of Environmental Laws, collected all the judgments on the Environmental science and Environmental Law. The motive of the review of literature is to prove the how the Role of National Green Tribunal is important in the Environmental Governance.

¹ Jain, Suresh. "Environmental Law in India." *Indian Journal of Public Administration* 31, no. 2 (1985): 424–30.

² Chadah, Sapna. "Environmental Law in India." *Indian Journal of Public Administration* 51, no. 2 (2005): 296–98.

4) COMPOSITION OF NATIONAL GREEN TRIBUNAL: -

The head office of National Green Tribunal is located at New Delhi. According to sec.4 of the national Green Tribunal Act,2010 it consists one full time chairperson who is retired judge of the supreme court of India, and judicial members of the National Green Tribunal is retired High Court Judges. As per sec. 4 the number of judicial members is minimum ten and maximum 20 members. In National Green tribunal also consists Expert members who possess the qualification of 15 years minimum experience in the subject of conservation and environment. The appointment of chairperson should be in consultation of the Chief Justice of India. The appointment of Judicial members and Expert Members is selected as per recommendations of selection committee as prescribed.³

Sec. 7 of the National Green tribunal Provided the term of office of the Chairperson and Members. As per sec. 7 the term of office of the chairperson, Judicial members and Expert members is five years from the date of appointment and there shall not be reappointment of the same persons who already hold offices.

Sec. 7 of the Act also provided that if the judge of the supreme court is appointed as Chairperson, judicial member, or expert member of the Tribunal he shall not hold any of the office after the age of seventy years.

And if the chief justice of the High Court has been appointed as chairperson, judicial member, or Expert member of the tribunal he shall not hold any of the office after the age of sixty-seven years. Also, it is provided that if the judge f the high Court is appointed as judicial member of the Tribunal he shall not hold any of the office after the age of sixty-seven years. Subsequently sec. 7 provided that expert member of the Tribunal shall not hold the office after completion of age sixty-five years.

5) POWERS OF NATIONAL GREEN TRIBUNAL: -

Chapter II of the National Green Tribunal Act deals with the Jurisdiction, Powers, and Proceedings of the Tribunal. It consists section 14 to 22.

According to sec. 14 the tribunal use the power of civil procedure code to settle the questions relating to environment. The tribunal also have a wide range of power of relief, compensation, and restitution. The National Green Tribunal deal with the various issues relating different types of Environmental Laws such as

³ Bare Act: The National Green Tribunal Act,2010.

- i) The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974;
- ii) The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Cess Act, 1977;
- iii) The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980;
- iv) The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981;
- v) The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986;
- vi) The Public Liability Insurance Act, 1991;
- vii) The Biological Diversity Act, 2002.

The National Green Tribunal settle the various cases relating to above laws. But the National Green Tribunal not hear the cases under Forest Act, 1927 and the wild Life Protection Act, 1972.

6) ROLE OF NATIONAL GREEN TRIBUNAL IN ENVIRONMENT GOVERNANCE: -

As a part of fundamental rights guaranteed by the constitution of India to every citizen the role of National green tribunal is very crucial to protect the right to life. The role of national green tribunal can be summarised under following grounds

- i) From the establishment the National Green Tribunal pass the important orders to prevent the Environmental Pollution and deforestation to waste management.
- ii) National green tribunal implement the principles of Environmental Jurisprudence by way of providing alternative dispute resolution system.
- iii) Because of establishment of National Green Tribunal, the burden of ligation reduced of the high Courts and Supreme Court of India.
- iv) It is proved that the National Green Tribunal is affordable and provide speedy justice to resolve the environmental cases.
- v) The National Green Tribunal prevent the damages from harmful environmental activities.
- vi) As a statutory compliance the chairperson and both judicial and Expert members are not eligible to reappointment therefore, they act independently and deliver a judgment on the merit of the case.
- vii) The national Green Tribunal instruct to the Government for Environment Impact Assessment.

7) JUDICIAL ACTIVISM AND NAIONAL GREEN TRIBUNAL: -

The National Green Tribunal is being a quasi-judicial body delivered so many decisions for the protection of Environment some of the decisions highlights here.

- 1) In the year 2012 one of the South Korean Steel Company made a MOU with The Government of Odisha to establish a project. The National Green Tribunal cancelled the said MOU on the ground of the said project is violation of the rights of the local people and it is against the conservation of forest.⁴
- 2) In the year 2012 in another case The National Green Tribunal decided to complete prohibition on open burning of waste on lands for the protection of environment.⁵
- 3) In another case in 2013 the National Green Tribunal decided about Uttarakhand located Aalagnanda Hydro Power Co. Ltd must pay to the petitioner the compensation on the principle of 'Polluter Pays'.⁶
- 4) In another case in 2013 the National Green Tribunal cancelled the Project having worth of 6400 Crore to save the habitant of the bird.⁷
- 5) Again in 2015 the National Green Tribunal declared the 10-year-old vehicles run on diesel will not be run to play in Delhi- NCR.
- 6) In the Year 2017 again, the National Green Tribunal held that the festival of Art Of Living on the Yamuna River violating the norms of Environmental law and imposed high penalty of Rs. 5 crores on the Group of Art of Living.
- 7) In 2017 the National Green Tribunal imposed a interim ban on plastic bag of 50-micron thickness in New Delhi.

8) CONCLUSION: -

After discussion on the various decisions given by the National Green Tribunal it can be said that the Role of National Green Tribunal is very Important in the protection of Environment and it can be suggested to the Government of India there should be widen the powers of the Tribunal and impose the time limitation on the disposal of the matter for speedy in justice to the affected applicants. Also, it can be suggested that the benches of the tribunal has to be increased and it will be good if the bench of National Green Tribunal is established in every State.

⁴ South Korean Steel Maker Co. Case (2012)

⁵ Almitra H. Patel Vs. UoI(2012)

⁶ Aalagnanda Hydro Power Co. Ltd Case (2013)

⁷ Mon Federation Vs. UOI Case(2013)

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